

IMPACTS OF EXTRAMARITAL AFFAIRS: LESSONS FOR SOCIAL WORKERS AND CHILD RIGHTS ADVOCATES

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Abstract: Apparently, extramarital affair is occurring in all communities with substantial negative socio-economic and political consequences both on the couples, children and the neighborhoods and deserves urgent attention to address it. The rationale for the systematic literature review is to interrogate the impacts of the phenomenon, share knowledge to spark and inspire processes that will command rapid growth from all directions. A systematic review of the literatures using information collected from different sources was actuated. Google search engine and others were used to search for articles. Only peer-reviewed articles published after 2000 were selected except extracts of fundamental mileage. However, articles published by staunch international organizations working in the area for years and produced indefatigable knowledge were stealthily appraised.

The study revealed that the impacts are numerous and entail: pressure on public institutions, abandoning the family, hatred and enmity, divorce and separation, anger and violent behaviors, mental instability, sexual dysfunctions, scapegoating children, low productivity and financial losses, posttraumatic stress disorders, transmission of diseases, conflict in the family, illegitimate children, depression and anxiety, living in guilt and shame; and personal growth.

Keywords: extramarital, sex, infidelity, impacts.

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Introduction

Marriage is one of the most fundamental contracts a man and a woman can enter into despite their numerous differences including their world view. Thus, commitment to the relationship to form a strong and healthy union, unified family and society is critical in any successful marriage (Atapour, Falsafinejad, Ahmadi, & Khodabakhshi-Koolae, 2021). Thus, it is a socially recognized and acceptable union, a legal contract between two unrelated individuals, usually a man and a woman that occurs in all human society (Odebode, James, Adegunju, & Julia, 2021).

Extramarital affairs the act of establishing and maintaining a sexual relationship outside a marriage with the anticipation of satisfying unmet needs which can be either physical, emotional or sexual has caused profound shock and dismay to many couples and their families (Stephen T. Fife, 2011). In modern societies despite the huge changes in boundaries including emotional relationships, extramarital affairs is unacceptable in many civilized societies but still it is a widespread practice demanding for urgent social attention and actions to eliminate it (Tsepapas, 2010). Seemingly, public attitudes towards marital infidelity is rapidly changing in some communities especially in the industrialized countries in which interestingly and increasingly, women, not men, are the first to stray from marriage, for example, in both the USA and the UK,

25% to 50% of the married women have at least one lover after they are married in any given marriage. Similarly, from 50% to 65% of the wedded men stray by the age of 40 (Adams, 2017). At present, 73% of the married people claimed to have had at least one affair. To reduce it with the ultimate objective of eliminating the behaviour in the society by prohibition, death by stoning is prescribed by Islamic laws in the event of adultery (UIA, 2020).

Extramarital sex is one of the factors threatening family structures and consequently the most fundamental sense of belonging, performance, stability, endurance of marital relationship (Waweru, 2022). Extramarital sexual relationship is common among all marriages in the United States of America with an estimate of 20% to 55% (Atkins, 2001), between 26% to 75% to be more precise (Eaves, 2007).

In the USA, one-third of all the divorces, at least one spouse has been involved in a marital infidelity behavior and as well, 34% of men and 19% of women in the adult groups in the USA have reported involvement in extramarital sexual relationships on one stage of their life (Messripour, Etemadi, Ahmadi, & Jazayeri, 2016). Even with the modest increment of 20% rate of extramarital affairs, one can safely suggest that it is prevalent and has eaten deep into the fabrics of marriages (Lişman & Holman, 2021). With the 20% to 25% of marital infidelity occurring in all marriages it is

certain that it has multiple deleterious effects on the relationships and the married couples themselves, their immediate and even distant family members (Zapien, 2017).

Marital infidelity, being a global problem, has caused tremendous effects on the society and has impacted differently different couples, socially, economically, psychologically, and culturally. Additionally, it is one of the most damaging behavior for the survival of marital relationship (Mapfumo, 2016). Most of the time if not all of the time, the damages inflicted by the discovery or revelation of marital infidelity can be very destructive not only to the marriage but to the entire family, the rebuilding of each can be time consuming and psychosocially expensive as it sometimes result in negative social, financial, medical, emotional, etc. impacts not mentioning separation, divorce, murder and suicides (Paul R. Amato, 2003). In addition to being the primary cause of divorce, spousal battering and other kind of domestic violence, it has no rival in disrupting marital relationship and worse of all, it is the third most difficult problem to resolve in marital problems, the fastest mean of spreading sexually transmitted infections including diseases such HIV/AIDS, thus making it a great public health issue in some communities (Allen & Atkins, 2012).

Methodology

A systematic review of the literatures using information collected from different sources was actuated. Google search engine, google scholar, web of science, scopus database, etc. were used to search for these articles. During the search numeration combinations of words and phrases were used to ensure articles reflect the most recent knowledge and scholarly works. The systematic searches beget varied and voluminous articles which had to be sieved not only to meet the inclusion and exclusion criteria but to ensure the fundamental objectives of the study are wrangled.

Therefore, only peer-reviewed scholarly publications published after 2000 were selected except extracts perceived to be of basal mileage to the study. However, articles published by staunch international organizations known to have been working in the promotion of healthy and stable family for years and has produced indefatigable knowledge in the area and related issues were stealthily appraised.

Inclusion and Exclusion Procedures

The underneath procedures were adopted in articles inclusion. That is, only:

1. Peer-reviewed scholarly articles on extramarital affairs.
2. Peer-reviewed scholarly articles published from 2000 to 2024.
3. Articles on international or regional perspectives on extramarital affairs and related issues.
4. Articles on extramarital affairs and related issues published by international organizations with years of meritorious experiences in the promotion of healthy and stable family.

To exclude some articles from the review, the below captioned criteria were applied. That is:

1. Non-peer reviewed articles.
2. Articles published before 2000 unless critical and impactful.
3. Media generated articles including newspapers.

4. Articles not published in English language.

In spite of the fact that both qualitative and quantitative articles were trawled, only 95 articles out of 217 were qualified for review which is largely due to a dearth of data. In essence, only peer-reviewed articles and publications by international organizations considered trustworthy because they occasioned standard, ethical; and robust studies were reviewed.

Discussions

The literature review has revealed a wide range of issues pertaining to extramarital affairs. To discuss the negative and positive impacts, they are classified into various thematic issues consisting of: pressure on public institutions, abandoning the family, hatred and enmity, divorce and separation, anger and violent behavior, mental instability, sexual dysfunctions, scapegoating children, low productivity and financial losses, posttraumatic stress disorder, transmission of diseases, conflict in the family, illegitimate children, depression and anxiety, living in guilt and shame; and personal growth.

Pressure on Public Institutions

Governments all over the globe have signed critical social contracts with their respective citizens placing some serious obligations on them to deliver (Seema Shah, 2022). To effectively deliver, governments have established different institutions with specialize tasks some of which are social, economic and political in nature. However, their effectiveness and efficient functioning have been threatened by several factors chief among them inadequate funding, corruption, demand related pressure, etc. leaving many citizens without some critical social services especially the vulnerable communities (Hanadi Sejar, 2022). In addition to the emotional, physical, mental costs, financial expenses related to extramarital infidelity, public institutions and programs bear some of the brunt of the negative externalities due to divorce like family fragmentation, single parenting, children dropping out of school, etc (Crouch & Dickes, 2016).

Abandoning the Family

The family being the building block of all societies is one of the most important social institutions ever created by humanity deserving lot of support and cooperation both internally and externally (Charlotte Nickerson, 2024). Over the years, the institution like most social institutions have witnessed some serious challenges which didn't only altered its structure and size but as well its ability to live up to expectation (Aart C. Liefbroer, 2009). These challenges being social or economic hardship in character has left many members including the innocent children and other members wallowing in serious problems including abandonment (Yassin Mohammed Yesuf, 2023) concurring with: because victims of marital infidelity are emotionally broken, they emotionally cut themselves off from any contact with their family members in an attempt to manage their disappointments (Siguan, Ong, & Canete, 2021). The post infidelity stress disorder, does not only lead to alcohol addiction, intense fear, hopelessness, terror, emotional numbness, heighten anxiety, irritability, rage, children avoiding their parents because of shame, mental and physical issues but also dead (Angelina & Marsih, 1945).

Hatred and Enmity

For communities and societies to develop and progress, social order and peaceful coexistence is fundamental (UN General

Assembly, 1968). This is more critical in the family, the building blocks of all societies and the chief architect of positive social interconnectedness, interdependence, non-warring values and norms, non-warring myths, rituals, symbols; and peaceful leadership (Fry, D.P., Souillac, G., Liebovitch, 2021). However, over the years families and communities have been seriously put under test due to several factors that can be socio-economic and political in perception. For communities and institutions that couldn't properly managed and resolved the associated problems and difficulties it has resulted in some constituencies being involved in different criminal and antisocial behaviors activities including extramarital affairs cultivating hatred and enmity even in the family, the most prestigious social institution (Sayani Basu, 2014) lending support to: psychologically women who are divorced because of marital infidelity suffer from different negative impacts namely; feelings of inferiority and worthless, fear and worry about their future, feeling sad and misery, regret and disappointment, anger, hate and heartache, hopeless, difficulty trusting men; and doubting about the self's ability to be responsible for growing up children and making them happy (Vina Witri Astuti & Lestari, 2022).

Separation and Divorce

Getting married in some communities is one of the biggest achievements for two adults as the marriage institution is one of the most noble and holiest institutions especially in highly religious communities (Ligonier Ministries, 2021). With marriage, peace and harmony is not only built in the hearts and minds of the couples but their families, friends and by extension the entire coming because a family constitute the most important social institution (Dr. Gunjan Jain, 2017). However, of recent, this holy institution has been threatened by numerous factors including infidelity resulting in separation at worst divorce one of the most unfortunate mishaps to the institution concurring with: the negative consequences of extramarital affairs entail divorce, emotional divorce; and trying to return back to normal at some costs (Atapour et al., 2021). Extramarital sex which is relatively common in the Western culture has resulted in many negative things such as battering loving and romantic relationship to the point of separation and divorce (Rokach & Chan, 2023). Extramarital affair is a serious social problem as it can lead to separation and even divorce if not professionally handled (Djamba, 2020). Marital infidelity is not only quoted as a critical turning point in a deteriorating relationship but one of the major contributors to divorce just like lack of commitment, conflicts and arguments, marrying too young, short dating period, economic problems, substance abuse; and domestic violence as endorsed by the majority of the participants (Scott, Rhoades, Stanley, Allen, & Markman, 2013).

Similarly, more than half of the men and women who are engage in extramarital sexual relationship end up with separation or divorce from their spouse (Allen & Atkins, 2012). Marital infidelity is one of the major causes of divorce and the ruining of marital life and relationship (Hatamy, Fathi, Gorji, & Esmaeily, 2011). The top twelve factors that can be associated with divorce and separation in most communities from the most to the least common are lack of commitment, constant arguing or conflict, infidelity, marrying too young, unrealistic expectations about partner or marriage, inequality between partners, inadequate preparation for marriage, domestic violence, financial problems, conflict about domestic

work, lack of open communication, intimacy, empathy, lack of family support, incompatibility; and religious differences (Jennifer Litner, 2022). Extramarital sex in addition to leading to divorce, it has some profound direct negative impacts on the couples such as depression, anxiety, posttraumatic stress disorder, financial loss, increase conflict and aggression similarly, the children are victimized by internalizing and externalizing the infidelity behavior (Erica A. Michell, 2023).

Anger and Violent Behavior

For any union to deliver effectively and efficiently the parties don't only need to understand all the clauses of the contract but they must foster and maintain a reasonable degree of mutual respect for each other and other stakeholders (Auer-Spath I, 2019). This automatically excludes anger and violent behaviors in the executing of a hitch free contract particularly in civilized and peace loving communities. However, over the decades societies have witnessed monumental increment in violent behaviors in different institutions including the family (Vickerman KA, 2008) which is attributable to series of factors encompassing antisocial behaviours such as extramarital affairs, domestic violence, third parties interference, etc. lending strength to: infidelity results in among others anger, fear, doubt, and repulsion (Fitness, 2006). In case of men extramarital relationship result in their feeling angry and being violent while for the women they feel sad and develop strong desire to seek compensatory relationship (Miller & Maner, 2008).

Mental Impairment

Health and long life is one of the greatest gifts to mankind as with good health a person can effectively and efficiently function for his or her personal progress being socio-economic and political (Jennifer Prah Ruger, 2003). However, being healthy is not only measured by the absence of diseases or infirmity but rather a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being (WHO, 1948). Thus, mental stability is a critical component of a person being healthy and fit for productive life and living. Of recent, the world has registered a surge in mental illness the causes of which are multifaceted (France 24, 2018) that include marital problems such as domestic violence and married couples involvement in extramarital relationships, concurring with: children who are victims of extramarital affairs suffer series of negative impacts that subsequently affect many aspects of their life including their mental health (Fitzgerald & Berthiaume, 2021). Extramarital affairs are a serious threat to psychological, emotional and mental health of the victims, leading to heighten depression, anxiety, stress; and battered self-esteem (Shrout, 2020).

Sexual Dysfunctions

Sex though one of the fundamental human rights of all adults, needs to be regulated to maintain peace and progress in the communities (Leatherman, 2007) by for example, preventing rape, sexual exploitation, violence and other forms of sexual relationship that violate the norms, values and laws of societies and nations (Elena Rubini, 2023). Over the decades, it has been regulated and monitored by the family, legislations, conventions and other specialized institutions through legally and traditionally recognized marriages (Koshan, J., 2016). However, recently, many communities have witnessed a surge in extramarital relationships due to numerous factors that doesn't only violate the holiness of the marriage institution but has caused endless problems among the married couples, families and by extension the wider communities

threatening coexistence among others (Alexandra E. Schmidt, 2016) more especially where proper management and resolutions failed to be rendered (Alyssa A. Drury, 2003). In the case of the married couples, it has significantly affected their sexual satisfaction because of the threat posed to love and loving concurring with: the four common negative impacts of marital infidelity and related behaviors include marked decrease in sexual activity and/or complete abstinence, marked increase in frequency, the development of sexual dysfunction and/or a shift in sexual behavior and/or expression (Tina Timm, 2022).

Scapegoating Children

In most contractual relationship including marriage healthy debate and reasonable misunderstanding is permissible as there is no perfect relationship (Zahra Sadat Asadi, 2016). However, it is highly recommended and welcome that anything of that nature is well managed and professionally addressed with critical lessons learned to avert similar things in the future (Tasew, 2021). In some instances, because of multifaceted factors, such problems are not completely addressed and keep surfacing causing harms with the weaker party suffering the most. In an attempt to revenge, the children are victimized just to anger the other party particularly in matrimonial homes rendering support to: as result of the overwhelming emotional trauma and pain, more often than not, some disappointed spouses overlook the fact that they sometimes project their anger and frustration towards the offspring rather than the unfaithful spouse (SIGUAN et al., 2021).

Low Productivity and Financial Losses

Seemingly, the progresses of every entity including the homes, to a degree depend on productivity and cooperation rather than unhealthy competition between the respective team members (Nataliia Rümmele, 2013). The productivity of any team player is hooked to several factors including being healthy which is not only the mere absence of diseases but being psychosocially fit as well (Jerome Bickenbach, 2015). Therefore to be productive and remain productive, being on high psychological gear is fundamental. However, because for married partners for his/her partner being involved in infidelity is a strong psychological slap (Kira Sly, 2021), their entire life is stricken resulting in serious economic and social shutdowns substantiating: marital infidelity, in addition to the direct impacts it has on the victims themselves, it has some serious negative impacts on the victims' execution of critical roles in the society such as delivery impairment to functioning, difficulty fulfilling roles, preoccupation, loss of identity, shame, getting stuck; and the inability to move on with life (Williams, 2019). The consequences of extramarital affair include financial loss or disruption, getting infected with diseases, becoming polygamous, getting better and improved services from a wife, wife improve on her physical appearances and romance, divorce, regrets, anxiousness; and also lack of overall satisfaction to some degrees (Ainun SajidahEvy MarlindaAgus Rachmadi, 2019).

Posttraumatic Stress Disorders

In many societies and communities getting married does not only bring the joy of having a sexual partner that one can claim to be legally his or her (Waite and Gallagher, 2000) but it significantly elevate one's health conditions (Corey Lee M. Keyes, 2015), socio-economic and political standing in the communities (Claire L Adida, 2013). In certain societies, particularly in Africa, a male is only considered to be a "really man and an adult" when he is

married and has started raising a family (Elyakim Kislev, 2022). Similarly, in some societies, because of being single, hardly unmarried men are consulted and considered in communities' issues and worse of all, even in their own families even if they are the eldest as they are considered irresponsible. In some instances, a person capability is questioned just because s/he is not married which may result in being denied a job otherwise being encouraged to get married immediately one succeed in getting the job or position (Abdul Feroz Maluleke, 2023). In some cases, married men earn more income than their single peers (W. Bradford Wilcox; Nicholas H. Wolfinger, 2018). Sometimes, unmarried men despite of their level of education and age are unjustifiable denied to lead prayers especially in fundamental Islamic communities (Islamicweb.net, 2008). In the case of the women, in some traditional communities, the unmarried ones are flatly denied political position in the communities as in the first instant they are never considered as serious women rather prostitutes (Yolanda Sadie, 2019). Therefore, in view of the personal sacrifices, financial expenses associated with getting married and the accrued or anticipated benefits of being married, any disappointment especially due to extramarital affairs particularly in small communities, the effects can be disturbing and traumatic lending support to: there was a statically fundamental association between depression among women and spouse who are survivors of marital infidelity (Kaggwa et al., 2021). Extramarital sexual relationships have resulted to various types of domestic conflicts among which is the exercitation of loneliness, depression, low self-esteem, dependence on social support/welfare, feeling betrayed; and sadness since intimacy is strangled and suffocated (Rokach & Philibert-lignièrès, 2015).

Transmission of Diseases

It seems there is an unprecedented increase in the diseases affecting the human race. Some including the noncommunicable ones are so serious that they have become a global threat requiring global actions to either eliminate them or help societies to cope with them till affordable treatment is discovered (Division of global health, 2021). Diseases especially the communicable ones are transmitted through different methods principal among them is the interaction with the person carrying such diseases. For instant, in the case of sexually transmitted infections (STIs), it is mostly spread by having sexual relationship with the victims (Seidu, AA., Agbaglo, E., Dadzie, 2021). In indiscriminate sexual affair like extramarital sex, the chances of one getting and/or transmitting diseases including HIV/AIDS are extremely high (Jennifer S. Hirsch, 2002) concurring with: extramarital relationship in addition to being a potential source for the transmission of sexually transmitted infections, other infections that can compromise the physical and mental health of victims, it is a romantic betrayal and insecurity, violation of victims' core beliefs and their significant others (Jules, O'Connor, & Langhinrichsen-Rohling, 2023). Marital infidelity leads to the acquisition of different negative health impacts including a range of sexually transmitted infections and diseases like chlamydia, gonorrhea, genital warts; and herpes (Kang & Pongou, 2020). Extramarital sexual relationship in addition to negatively impacting on partners' moral and psychological development, it is significantly associated with the spread of diseases in the communities (Jahan et al., 2017). In India, the number of married men contracting sex workers is on the increase which mostly occurs in the high-HIV states/provinces

shooting up/escalating the pandemic prevalence (Gaffey et al., 2011).

In Cambodia, the liberal attitudes toward extramarital sex has played a significant part in the increase of HIV/AIDS spread among spouses (Thapa, Yang, & Nget, 2019). Women engaged in extramarital sex are negatively impacted in different ways for example; it takes heavy toll on their physical and emotional health by being subject to abuse by the men and the pimps in some cases (Schwartz's Weblog, 2011). Without intervention to curb extramarital sexual activities in India, the spread of HIV/STI in matrimonial homes is likely to be catapulted (Schensul et al., 2006).

Conflict in the Family

It is natural that nearly all were born in a family and majority would like to live and died in a family as a fundamental human right well-articulated in both Article 16 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights and Article 23 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (United Nations, 2023). Thus, family is very critical in the life and living conditions of many if not all of us. In the family, members are not only provided with their basic needs but also protected from both internal and external harms being physical, psychological and sexual in nature (Balistreri & Alvira-Hammond, 2016). Conflict though can be harmful, is almost unavoidable in a community, group and even the family. Therefore, human beings are identical with a difference, learning and mastering its prevention, resolution and management strategies is a must to all for harmonious and nostalgic living (Bunyamin Maftuf, 2021). The sources of family conflict are several principal among them is cheating on each other especially the married couples. Therefore, married couples having extramarital affairs potentially expose their families to conflict and possible disintegration via separation, abandonment and divorce if not properly managed and addressed (Rokach A, 2023) reaffirming: to effectively prevent extramarital sex and divorce among married couples, it is critical they are provided the necessary support to ensure there is sexual satisfaction in the marital homes as it decreases instability and conflicts (Shakerian, Nazari, Masoomi, Ebrahimi, & Danai, 2014)

Illegitimate Children

To many families even communities, societies, nations the arrival of a new born child is a huge joy celebrated in different manners. However, in some communities there are well established legal and moral procedures through which children are acquired otherwise their arrival can be viewed as family betrayal and abomination warranting the unjustifiable abuse and maltreatment of the illegitimate children and their parents particularly the mothers (Garry F. Almazan, 2021). For instant, children are acquired by families through natural deliveries and/or adoption. In whichever way, the laydown rules and regulations must be strictly followed to avoid the illegal arrival of a child. In most societies the legality and illegality of the arrival of a child is determined the legal consummation of a marriage between two consenting adults more especial a man and a woman (Andrew Symon, 2008). Therefore, any child born outside a legally recognized marriage is regarded as illegitimate child. In discriminate sexual relations including extramarital affairs can result to the delivery of illegitimate children with profound negative consequences on both the child and the marriage (Iffatin Nur, 2015) substantiating: marital infidelity has negatively impacted couples and their relationships in

different fundamental ways that include divorce, illegitimate children, group sex, prostitution, marital instability, publicly humiliated spouses; and honor killing (UIA, 2020). The aftermath of infidelity includes but not limited to giving birth to illegitimate children, psychological trauma in children, destruction and suspicion in the family, hatred in the family, unwanted pregnancy, divorce, unhappiness, contraction of sexually transmitted diseases, emotional disabilities (Odebode et al., 2021).

Depression and Anxiety

To remain healthy, productive and successful in life requires lot of things principal among them is good health (Mehmood, Aqsa and Siddique & Ali, 2022). To acquire this all yearning status, one must be physically, socially, psychologically and emotionally fit. Similarly, to be psychologically and emotional balance one needs a peaceful mind that cannot be attain in a tormenting and disappointing environment particularly in a relationship and habitation which is meant to be supportive, complementary and for life such as marriage (Halpern-Meekin S, Manning WD, Giordano PC, 2013). Thus, as disappointing as extramarital affairs are, if not prevented and addressed adequately, it can be a great source of psychological and emotional problems, depression and anxiety inclusive (Marin R. Wenger, 2020) concurring with: betrayal due to infidelity can leads to PTSD, depression, anxiety, dissociation, difficulty in concentration, emotional dysregulation, trust and relationship issues, physical pain and gastrointestinal issues, substance abuse; and eating disorders (Gupta, 2023). Anxiety, depression, anger, self-loathing, hysterical bonding; and low self-esteem are common negative impacts of marital infidelity (Tristan McBain, 2022). There was a statically fundamental association between depression among women and spouse who are survivors of marital infidelity (Kaggwa et al., 2021).

Living In Guilt and Shame

Progressive development being at individual, family or community level is inseparable from steady and peaceful mind. To attain and maintain such a fundamental requisite, trust in each other is critical (Irsa fatima makhdoom, 2019). Thus, any iota of mistrust and betrayal, extramarital sex being inclusive can be disastrous to others and the perpetrator himself or herself resulting in the living in guilt and shame which if not professionally handled and addressed can have profound negative impacts on the perpetrator and his or her circle of social networks including the family (Matthijs Kalmijn, 2020) concurring with: while victims of marital infidelity live in trauma, the perpetrators live in shame and guilt soberly begging for support to come out of such toxic behavior (Camp Taylor, 2016).

Personal Growth

In many instances, it has been claimed that every act including development which we all cherish has some positive and negative effects. For instant, though classic roads are critical in the socio-economic development of societies and nations it has been alleged that they catapult the increment in car fatal road accidents (Simon Armand Zogo Tsala, 2020). Astonishingly, immoral acts that are purely and hugely associated with the unprecedented increase in conflict and instability in the communities including the families are claimed to have some positive impacts on the perpetrators and the community as substantiated: infidelity could favor adolescents' personal growth, because of the need to explore new sensations and feelings that arise during this period (Beltrán-Morillas, 2020).

The consequences of extramarital affair include financial loss or disruption, getting infected with diseases, becoming polygamous, divorce, regrets, anxiousness but also getting better and improved services from a wife, wife improve on her physical appearances and romance; and overall satisfaction to some degrees (Ainun SajidahEvy MarlindaAgus Rachmadi, 2019).

Summary and conclusions

In brief, the impacts of extramarital relationship include pressure on public institutions, abandoning the family, hatred and enmity, divorce and separation, anger and violent behaviors, mental instability, sexual dysfunctions, scapegoating children, low productivity and financial losses, posttraumatic stress disorders, transmission of diseases, conflict in the family, illegitimate children, depression and anxiety, living in guilt and shame; and personal growth. For simplicity, these can be pooled and catalogued into social, cultural, economic and psychosocial impacts.

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